

Quantum simulation in imaginary time for gauge-invariant models

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Abstract

We provide a method for (i) performing deterministic imaginary time evolution and (ii) computing the thermal average of gauge-invariant models. We assess scalability on quantum computers, employing a circuit-based formulation. We validate our framework by numerical simulations of two- and three-particle chains. Results show that the method is correct within a finite-temperature regime and may be used to approximate ground-state energies.

Quantum computing in imaginary time is a well-established technique for computing the ground state energy of a Hamiltonian [8, 9, 5, 4]. While it is generally infeasible to simulate an imaginary time evolution using classical binary computation, quantum computers are in principle more suitable, due to their natural ability to encode physical systems into qubits. However, practical implementations inevitably involve stochastic errors, which are typically addressed through heuristic corrections [8] or by discarding failed experimental runs [5]. We propose an algorithm that, although stochastic, guarantees correct results. We demonstrate its correctness on gauge-invariant models [10, 13, 3] and validate it through numerical calculations of thermal averages [12].

Figure 1: Circuit realization of $e^{\pm\frac{\beta}{2}\gamma Z}$ on second qubit.

1 Quantum circuits for imaginary time

Consider the Hamiltonian $H = \gamma Z$. The circuit in Fig. 1 realizes the following imaginary time evolution:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \pm \frac{\beta\gamma}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \mp \frac{\beta\gamma}{2} \end{bmatrix} \approx e^{\pm \frac{\beta\gamma}{2} Z}. \quad (1)$$

The sign is random and depends on the auxiliary qubit, initialized to $|+\rangle$ – see Appendix A.

The circuit generalizes to any Pauli exponentiation – e.g. via Clifford transformations [1]. For example, circuit in Fig. 2 reads $e^{\pm \frac{\beta\gamma}{2}(X \otimes X)}$. Any given Pauli operator $P_1 \otimes P_2 \otimes \dots \otimes P_n$ requires a circuit with one auxiliary qubit and $\mathcal{O}(n)$ gates. The complexity reduces to $\mathcal{O}(1)$ if the quantum computer supplies Pauli exponentiation as a native gate.

Figure 2: Basis transformation for $H = X \otimes X$.

Sticking to $H = \gamma Z$, let us visualize the two possible evolutions on a Bloch sphere – see Fig. 3. The operator $e^{\pm \frac{\beta\gamma}{2} Z}$ drives $|+\rangle$ toward some eigenstate of H , with convergence at $\beta\gamma = \pi/2$. This remains true for any given input, possibly being a mixed state [15, 11].

The approach in [8] is equivalent:

$$\langle 0 | e^{-i\beta Y \otimes H} | + \rangle, \langle 1 | e^{-i\beta Y \otimes H} | + \rangle. \quad (2)$$

The measurement outcome drives the system into either $e^{-\beta H}$ or $e^{+\beta H}$. However, using one auxiliary qubit for the entire Hamiltonian requires direct realization of $e^{-i\beta Y \otimes H}$, compromising the accuracy [6]. Differently, we assign an auxiliary qubit to each Pauli operator of H . As we proceed, we show that our approach seems feasible for models that feature a gauge-invariance, as in [10]. As a proof-of-concept, we address the transverse Ising model and the XY model.

Figure 3: Bloch sphere representation of $e^{\pm \frac{\beta\gamma}{2} \gamma Z} |+\rangle$.

2 Gauge-invariant models

2.1 Transverse Ising model

Let H be the Hamiltonian for the transverse Ising one- or two-dimensional lattice. The one-dimensional case reads:

$$H = \sum_j \gamma_j (Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1}) + \eta \sum_j X_j. \quad (3)$$

There exists a Gauge transformation [10] for which H is invariant. This leads our focus to the following unitary transformation:

$$UHU^\dagger \rightarrow \sum_j \gamma_j (\pm 1) (Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1}) + \eta \sum_j (\pm 1) X_j. \quad (4)$$

Inherently, the energy spectrum is common to every configuration of signs and

$$\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta UHU^\dagger}) = \text{Tr}(Ue^{-\beta H}U^\dagger) = \text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H}). \quad (5)$$

We exploit (5) to define a quantum algorithm that computes $\langle H \rangle_\beta$ – i.e. the thermal average. Specifically, by mapping a maximally mixed state $\frac{\mathbb{1}}{\dim(H)}$ – see Appendix B – into the thermal state

$$\frac{e^{-\beta UHU^\dagger}}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta UHU^\dagger})} = \frac{1}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H})} \sum_n e^{-\beta \lambda_n} U|n\rangle\langle n|U^\dagger, \quad (6)$$

with $H|n\rangle = \lambda_n|n\rangle$ and U determined by the auxiliary system. With knowledge of U , the thermal average of H is given:

$$\frac{1}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H})} \sum_{n,m} e^{-\beta \lambda_n} \langle m|U^\dagger U|n\rangle \langle n|U^\dagger U H|m\rangle = \frac{1}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H})} \sum_n e^{-\beta \lambda_n} \lambda_n. \quad (7)$$

Considering the linearity of expectation

$$\langle H \rangle_\beta = \sum_j \gamma_j \langle Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1} \rangle_\beta + \eta \sum_j \langle X_j \rangle_\beta, \quad (8)$$

partial measurements over Z and X observables establish full characterization.

As an exemplary circuit realization, see Fig. 4 for a two-spin system, with two steps of Trotter decomposition [2]. Notice that the corrections determined by the auxiliary qubits can be classical, because of the deferred-measurement principle.

Figure 4: Two-spin system with two steps of Trotter decomposition.

2.2 XY model

The XY model [3] is another well-established representation featuring Gauge invariance. For the one-dimensional case it reads:

$$H = \sum_j \gamma_j (X_j \otimes X_{j+1} + Y_j \otimes Y_{j+1}). \quad (9)$$

It is a special case of the gauge glass in [10] and it is invariant under local signs flips:

$$UHU^\dagger \rightarrow \sum_j \gamma_j(\pm 1)(X_j \otimes X_{j+1} + Y_j \otimes Y_{j+1}). \quad (10)$$

Notice that the terms $X_j \otimes X_{j+1}$ and $Y_j \otimes Y_{j+1}$ appear together with the same sign (isotropic configuration). The alternating–sign configuration (anisotropic) and the isotropic configuration are not unitarily equivalent. However, they are isospectral and possess spectrally symmetric eigenvalues. Therefore, our method can be applied to Eq. (9), by eventually flipping the sign to the estimated energy. Specifically, Fig. 5 shows the implementation of a three-particle chain with two step of Trotter decomposition.

Figure 5: Three particle chain system with two steps of Trotter decomposition.

3 Circuits based on the Zassenhaus formula

What we introduced so far gives enough information for our comprehension of the framework. While the aim of this section is improving the experiment

performance by employing a formulation that is more precise than basic Trotter decomposition.

Let us treat the non-commuting operators in H of Eq. (3) according to the Zassenhaus formula [7]. We expand $e^{-\beta H}$ with a second-degree truncation:

$$\prod_j e^{\beta^2 \frac{\eta}{2} (\gamma_j [Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1}, X_j] + \gamma_{j+1} [Z_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2}, X_{j+1}])} \prod_j e^{-\beta \gamma_j (Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1})} \prod_j e^{-\beta \eta X_j}. \quad (11)$$

The operators $[Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1}, X_j]$ and $[Z_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2}, X_{j+1}]$ do not commute. Hence, by recursion we have:

$$e^{\beta^2 \eta \gamma_j (Y_j \otimes Z_{j+1})} e^{\beta^2 \eta \gamma_{j+1} (Y_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2})} e^{-\beta^4 \frac{\eta^2}{2} [\gamma_j (Y_j \otimes Z_{j+1}), \gamma_{j+1} (Y_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2})]}. \quad (12)$$

Last commutator may be neglected, otherwise it solves:

$$[\gamma_j (Y_j \otimes Z_{j+1}), \gamma_{j+1} (Y_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2})] = 2\gamma_j \gamma_{j+1} (Y_j \otimes X_{j+1} \otimes Z_{j+2}). \quad (13)$$

Notice that each introduced factor is a Pauli exponentiation and admits direct circuit realization. As discussed, there are random signs determined by the auxiliary system. But, because of eq. (5), we can measure the auxiliary qubits and find the corresponding transformation U . More specifically, we check the outcomes referring to $e^{\pm\beta\gamma(Z_j \otimes Z_{j+1})}$ and $e^{\pm\beta\eta X_j}$. There is no need to check the other operators. In fact, their randomness generates evolutions that differ only by the sign of the imaginary part, and are equivalent when computing $\langle H \rangle_\beta$. See Fig. 6 for the circuit realizing a first-degree Zassenhaus expansion.

Figure 6: Two qubits with first-degree Zassenhaus expansion.

Figure 7: Thermal average for the transverse spin chain with Zassenhaus first-degree decomposition.

4 Results

We validate our framework through classical simulation of a quantum computer, in the scenario of two and three particles. Let us set the parameters to their maximum available – i.e. $\gamma_j = \eta = \pi/4$ –, as it is the case where Trotter decomposition performs the worst. We compare the quantum computation with the exact solution within a high-temperature regime and first-degree Zassenhaus expansion. Fig. 7 shows that our method captures the actual decay of the thermal expectation value, both for two and three particles.

With the next experimental set we evaluate how close we can get to the ground state energy of a system. We here combine Zassenhaus formula with Trotter decomposition, enabling precise simulation along with greater β values. Fig. 8 refers to the a two-particle spin chain and a three-particle XY chain. Both for spin chain and XY chain the simulation gets very close to the actual ground state energy.

5 Discussion

This work introduces a framework for the computation of thermal averages in quantum systems via imaginary time evolution, designed to be both *accurate* and computationally *efficient*. We focus on the Gauge-invariant models. This choice allows us to exploit the model’s symmetry from [10] and, in principle, it may extend to other systems [14].

A key advantage of our framework is the ability to characterize the decay

Figure 8: Thermal average for TFIM (a) and XY model (b).

of thermal average in a systematic way, offering an alternative to heuristic-based solutions [8].

Providing an exact realization of imaginary-time evolution often requires discarding experimental runs [5], which reduces computational efficiency. In this work, we present a method to achieve exact simulation in every run, eliminating the need to discard experiments.

Taken together, these elements support our initial claim: the proposed method provides accurate results while keeping resource requirements low, making it a promising tool for the study of quantum models with exploitable symmetries.

6 Conclusion

The aim of this work has been twofold: (i) to implement imaginary time evolution and (ii) to compute the thermal average of selected quantum many-body systems. These represent two computational challenges that are, in many cases, intractable for classical computers, due to the exponential scaling of resources with system size. This limitation motivates the exploration of alternative strategies, and quantum computing naturally emerges as a promising route to address such problems. In this context, the present work contributes an additional step toward the practical realization of quantum algorithms specifically tailored for tackling physically relevant tasks. Looking ahead, there are several promising directions for future research. One avenue would be to extend the framework to encompass a broader class of quantum systems, particularly those with symmetries. Another would be to investigate

the applicability of the method to high-dimensional models, with the ultimate goal of testing its performance on real quantum hardware.

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References

- [1] J. Dehaene and B. De Moor. Clifford group, stabilizer states, and linear and quadratic operations over $gf(2)$. *Physical Review A*, 68(4):042318, 2003.
- [2] I. Dhand and B. C. Sanders. Stability of the trotter–suzuki decomposition. *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical*, 47(26), 2014.
- [3] S. Friedli and Y. Velenik. *Statistical mechanics of lattice systems: a concrete mathematical introduction*. Cambridge University Press, 2017.
- [4] M. Kondappan, M. Chaudhary, E. O. Ilo-Okeke, V. Ivannikov, and T. Byrnes. Imaginary-time evolution with quantum nondemolition measurements: Multiqubit interactions via measurement nonlinearities. *Physical Review A*, 107(4), 2023.
- [5] C. Leadbeater, N. Fitzpatrick, D. M. Ramo, and A. J. Thom. Non-unitary trotter circuits for imaginary time evolution. *Quantum Science and Technology*, 9(4), 2024.
- [6] G. H. Low and I. L. Chuang. Hamiltonian simulation by qubitization. *Quantum*, 3:163, 2019.
- [7] W. Magnus. On the exponential solution of differential equations for a linear operator. *Communications on pure and applied mathematics*, 7(4):649–673, 1954.

- [8] Y. Mao, M. Chaudhary, M. Kondappan, J. Shi, E. O. Ilo-Okeke, V. Ivanikov, and T. Byrnes. Measurement-based deterministic imaginary time evolution. *Physical Review Letters*, 131(11), 2023.
- [9] S. McArdle, T. Jones, S. Endo, Y. Li, S. C. Benjamin, and X. Yuan. Variational ansatz-based quantum simulation of imaginary time evolution. *npj Quantum Information*, 5(1):75, 2019.
- [10] S. Morita, Y. Ozeki, and H. Nishimori. Gauge theory for quantum spin glasses. *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan*, 75(1), 2006.
- [11] M. A. Nielsen and I. L. Chuang. *Quantum computation and quantum information*. Cambridge university press, 2010.
- [12] J. Perk, H. Capel, G. Quispel, and F. Nijhoff. Finite-temperature correlations for the ising chain in a transverse field. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 123(1):1–49, 1984.
- [13] R. Stinchcombe. Ising model in a transverse field. i. basic theory. *Journal of Physics C: Solid State Physics*, 6(15):2459, 1973.
- [14] R. van Leeuwen. Revealing symmetries in quantum computing for many-body systems. *New Journal of Physics*, 26(10):103023, 2024.
- [15] M. M. Wilde. *Quantum information theory*. Cambridge university press, 2013.

A Circuit derivation

Circuit in Fig.1 uses an auxiliary qubit initialized to state $|+\rangle$ and it works on any state $|\varphi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$.

The initial state is

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\alpha|00\rangle + \beta|01\rangle + \alpha|10\rangle + \beta|11\rangle) \quad (14)$$

The first three gates are the standard decomposition of an Ising gate. We are essentially applying the following unitary operation:

$$e^{i\vartheta(Z\otimes Z)} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-i\vartheta} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\vartheta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & e^{i\vartheta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & e^{-i\vartheta} \end{bmatrix},$$

with $-\frac{\pi}{4} \leq \vartheta \leq +\frac{\pi}{4}$.

Next gate occurring is

$$\sqrt{X} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1+i & 1-i \\ 1-i & 1+i \end{bmatrix}.$$

By applying \sqrt{X} to the auxiliary qubit, the system state results to have four terms:

- $\frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}(e^{-i\vartheta} + e^{+i\vartheta} + ie^{-i\vartheta} - ie^{+i\vartheta})|00\rangle \approx \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + \vartheta)|00\rangle$
- $\frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}(e^{+i\vartheta} + e^{-i\vartheta} - ie^{+i\vartheta} + ie^{-i\vartheta})|01\rangle \approx \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - \vartheta)|01\rangle$
- $\frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{2}}(e^{+i\vartheta} + e^{-i\vartheta} - ie^{+i\vartheta} + ie^{-i\vartheta})|10\rangle \approx \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}(1 - \vartheta)|10\rangle$
- $\frac{\beta}{2\sqrt{2}}(e^{-i\vartheta} + e^{+i\vartheta} + ie^{-i\vartheta} - ie^{+i\vartheta})|11\rangle \approx \frac{\beta}{\sqrt{2}}(1 + \vartheta)|11\rangle.$

Measuring the auxiliary qubit generates two possible evolutions, namely:

$$\alpha(1 + \vartheta)|0\rangle + \beta(1 - \vartheta)|1\rangle, \quad (15)$$

at case $\langle 0|+\rangle$; and

$$\alpha(1 - \vartheta)|0\rangle + \beta(1 + \vartheta)|1\rangle \quad (16)$$

at case $\langle 1|+\rangle$.

B Input a maximally mixed state

In order to prepare a maximally mixed state $\mathbb{1}/d$, one can start from preparing a maximally entangled pure state

$$|\varphi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \sum_n^d |n\rangle|n\rangle$$

The corresponding density matrix is

$$|\varphi\rangle\langle\varphi| = \frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d \sum_m^d |n\rangle|n\rangle\langle m|\langle m| = \frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d \sum_m^d |n\rangle\langle m| \otimes |n\rangle\langle m|.$$

Let us apply a partial trace over the second qubit:

$$\text{Tr}_2\left[\frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d \sum_m^d |n\rangle\langle m| \otimes |n\rangle\langle m|\right] = \frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d \sum_m^d |n\rangle\langle m| \cdot \text{Tr}[|n\rangle\langle m|].$$

Which results to be equivalent to the target state:

$$\frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d \sum_m^d |n\rangle\langle m| \delta_{nm} = \frac{1}{d} \sum_n^d |n\rangle\langle n| = \frac{\mathbb{1}}{d}.$$